

Listening to locals? Question-oriented approach in Field Lab Amsterdam East

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Abstract

A question-oriented approach is a popular and, in many cases, recommended *modus operandi* these days. However, it can be misleading, and unless properly understood and put into practice it may seem a mere semantic trick.¹⁵ It should therefore be evident whose question is the focus of attention. Taking residents' wishes as a starting point calls for a more precise definition of the target group. Residents come in all sorts with many different views and needs. In the context of a fieldlab, identifying bottom-up issues from the start is a difficult assignment. Nowadays a question-oriented approach is widespread in dealing with all kinds of local issues. No local proposal is accepted without a prior 'bottom-up' consultation of residents regarding their needs and ideas. On paper, a question-oriented approach may appear feasible, but in practice it proves to be anything but. Starting with the question: Who is the requesting party? The residents only or could the researcher, the city council and the financier also have a say in the selection of the issue and how it will be handled? This paper describes how the question-oriented approach was applied in an area based fieldlab developed by the Amsterdam University of Applied (AUAS) in a neighbourhood in Amsterdam East.

¹⁵ Majoor, Stan (2016). *De stad als experiment. De organisatie van stedelijke innovatie*. Inaugural address for the Lectorate, Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences; Majoor, Stan (2016). 'Inleiding' in: *Werken in een gebied: gewoon doen in Amsterdam*. Amsterdam Municipality: Project Management Bureau. pp. 7-13; Karré, P.M., Vanhommerig, I. & Van Bueren, E., 'De stad als lab voor sociale verandering', In: *Bestuurskunde*, Vol. 24:1, 2015

1 Question-oriented approach

Question-oriented methods seem to be a counter-reaction to a period in which administrations and market forces more so than the end user determined the appearance of a renovated square, the types of care available in a neighbourhood, and the frequency of local green maintenance.¹⁶ During the last decade, the position of the end user, often the resident, in the political governance arena has changed considerably.¹⁷ This is visible in among others the energy and housing sector and the health care. It has different causes. Residents are seen as a valuable source of information and for developing more effective policies. They are expected to become involved in and take responsibility for their environment, allowing the government to step back in some situations. At the same time, some residents wish to have more influence on policies, since they believe they can do it better, faster, cheaper.¹⁸ Whatever the case may be, from now on public professionals are expected to operate 'bottom-up'. The systems world reaches out to the lifeworld. The implications for public professionals are that they have to start operating on the basis of what residents ask of them or need from them.

The danger of the popularity of the question-oriented strategy, in which residents are the surveyed party, is that it may lead to a less rigorous assessment of the suitability of the strategy in each situation. Moreover, among involved and consulted parties the novel nature of a question-oriented approach raises high expectations which may not always be lived up to.¹⁹ After all, not all proposed issues lend themselves well to being dealt with locally and by local professionals and researchers.²⁰ Also, there are frequent collisions between, on the one hand, the power of the comprehensive body of local knowledge and the novel solutions and, on the other, a market party or a compartmentalized administration based outside the area.²¹ Finally, the expression 'bottom-up' implies a new method, as if earlier projects were not equally question-

¹⁶ Majoor, Stan (2016). *De stad als experiment. De organisatie van stedelijke innovatie*. Inaugural address for the Lectorate, Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences

¹⁷ Wetenschappelijke Raad voor het Regeringsbeleid. (2012). *Vertrouwen in burgers*. Den Haag: Amsterdam University Press

¹⁸ Ibidem

¹⁹ Smit, H. & Wassenberg, F. (2015), 'Wie geeft vorm aan de gebouwde stad?'. In: *De stad kennen, de stad maken: De gebouwde stad*. Platform 31.; Karré, Philip, Vanhommerig, Iris & Van Bueren, Ellen (2015). 'De stad als lab voor sociale verandering', *Bestuurskunde*, 24(1), pp. 3-11.; Vliet, K. van, (2002). 'Vraaggericht werken'. In: L. Verplanke, R. Engbersen, J.W. Duyvendak, E. Tonkens & K. van Vliet (eds) (2002). *Open deuren. Sleutelwoorden van lokaal sociaal beleid*. Utrecht: NIZW/Verwey-Jonker Instituut

²⁰ Majoor, Stan (2016). 'Inleiding' in: *Werken in een gebied: gewoon doen in Amsterdam*. Amsterdam Municipality: Project Management Bureau

²¹ Majoor, Stan (2016). *De stad als experiment. De organisatie van stedelijke innovatie*. Inaugural address for the Lectorate, Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences; Smit, H. & Wassenberg, F. (2015), 'Wie geeft vorm aan de gebouwde stad?'. In: *De stad kennen, de stad maken: De gebouwde stad*. Platform 31

oriented and based on collaboration with end users.²²

An interesting aspect of a question-oriented approach is that the term ‘question-oriented’ almost always refers to ‘the’ question of ‘the’ resident: the resident as the main end user of the solution. Question-oriented implies that those asking the question make the first step, followed by a response which reflects that question.²³ This is suggestive of one-way traffic: administrations reach out to citizens and the citizens formulate their needs. The administration is no longer supposed to be a supplier of services, but a mediator between various different parties.²⁴ What is needed is a mutual, local interplay of give and take, for the very reason that what residents are asking for is seldom clear-cut. The definition of the question is preceded by a process of listening, attuning and redefining what is needed. A commonly used definition of a question-oriented approach is therefore: establishing a match between what is available and the (subjective) needs of residents in a process of ongoing interaction between government, institutions and residents.²⁵

It is this interaction between parties which the fieldlab facilitates. This process involves more than the multiple needs of residents. In the dynamics of co-creation several parties have a question and are looking for a matching answer through an experiment driven learning process. It is up to the fieldlab team, in the case of Amsterdam East consisting of a fieldlab coordinator, a professor and a government representative, to investigate the relationships between these different requesting parties; the residents, the researchers, the public professionals and the financiers.

2 A resilient neighbourhood

Since its 2007-2011 neighbourhood renovation, Amsterdam-East has been an area with an abundance of resident initiatives, neighbourhood communities and a local administration who provides the opportunities and means to facilitate and stimulate these dynamics at grassroots level. Experimentation with neighbourhood budgets and social tender is lively. In short: East is dynamic and ambitious in finding new

²² Karré, Philip, Vanhommerig, Iris & Van Bueren, Ellen (2015). ‘De stad als lab voor sociale verandering’, *Bestuurskunde*, 24(1), pp. 3-11; Majoor, Stan (2016). *De stad als experiment. De organisatie van stedelijke innovatie. Inaugural address for the Lectorate, Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences*

²³ Vliet, K. van, (2002). ‘Vraaggericht werken’. In: L. Verplanke, R. Engbersen, J.W. Duyvendak, E. Tonkens & K. van Vliet (eds) (2002). *Open deuren. Sleutelwoorden van lokaal sociaal beleid*. Utrecht: NIZW/Verwey-Jonker Instituut; Smit, H. & Wassenberg, F. (2015), ‘Wie geeft vorm aan de gebouwde stad?’. In: *De stad kennen, de stad maken: De gebouwde stad*. Platform 31

²⁴ Ibidem

²⁵ Vliet, K. van, (2002). ‘Vraaggericht werken’. In: L. Verplanke, R. Engbersen, J.W. Duyvendak, E. Tonkens & K. van Vliet (eds) (2002). *Open deuren. Sleutelwoorden van lokaal sociaal beleid*. Utrecht: NIZW/Verwey-Jonker Instituut, p. 230

approaches to local democracy. The question is how East, despite current budget cuts and administrative shifts, will be able to sustain this energy.²⁶ Could it become even more attuned to its residents and smarter in working with all sorts of stakeholders? That was the main question the urban district East asked the fieldlab to investigate. This question matched the fieldlab's own ambition to contribute to a resilient neighbourhood. One where residents, business owners and others would be given the space and be relied upon to do what would make them and their neighbourhood resilient.²⁷ The implication of this ambition was that the definition and approach of the issues should centre on the neighbourhood. But how can a large knowledge institute, like the AUAS, with researchers who are partly unfamiliar with the dynamics and characteristics of East and who depend on earmarked, project-specific funding, set up a bottom-up strategy? And this, moreover, whilst partnering with urban district East, which has its own agenda and urgencies. This was the first challenge of the AUAS fieldlab team.²⁸

3 The requesting party

In order to get a general idea of current issues in urban district East in the start-up phase, the fieldlab team organized two public work meetings for key actors in Fieldlab East.²⁹ In the course of the search for potential fieldlab projects, the team questioned a number of local administrators, the secretary of the urban district council, neighbourhood actors and AUAS representatives. Based on this information, the team wrote an action plan, in which it proposed certain issues and potential stakeholders. Meanwhile, three professors had joined the fieldlab team. They were interested in conducting research in East and their studies tied in with the broad themes contained in Fieldlab East's Action Plan. A situation arose in which a search for a research area was accompanied by an offer by the professors to provide possible methods and techniques. At the same time the local council's call for support for its employees who were working in the neighbourhoods grew louder. This request occurred against a backdrop of the abolition of urban districts as administrative body, a centralization of resources and expertise, and a greater focus on area-based

²⁶ From 2010 onwards several municipal reorganizations and budget cuts were implemented (*Een stad, een opgave (Binnenlands Bestuur, May 23, 2013)*). In 2017, urban district budgets were reduced by 7 million euro; this will be 10.5 million in 2018 and 14 million in 2019 (Parool, 21 September, 2016). In 2018, as part of the most recent administrative reforms, the seven urban district councils will be abolished

²⁷ As also stated in Fieldlab Oost's *110 Dagen Plan, 2014*

²⁸ The priority area Urban Management of the AUAS started in 2015 with three area based fieldlabs in three deprived neighbourhoods of Amsterdam.

²⁹ Unlike Fieldlab Nieuw West, Fieldlab Oost did not select an area beforehand to situate its projects. Ultimately, Fieldlab Oost carried out its three projects in three different neighbourhoods.

approaches.³⁰

Each of the three parties - neighbourhood, urban district council and professors - was keen to use the fieldlab to fulfil its own needs. In hindsight, the fact that the neighbourhood in the end drew the short straw in the ultimate selection of problems and areas was to some extent to be expected in the light of the *110 Days Plan*. Despite its focus on question-oriented approach and resident-controlled local development, the plan's chapter 'The Players' barely mentions the residents as partners. Not exactly an appealing invitation for a question (read resident)-oriented experiment.

A similar trend can be observed in the projects' execution. In the context of one of Fieldlab East projects, the Age Friendly City (AFC) project, the neighbourhood was regarded as a suitable study area rather than an end user with a specific question. What's more, the search for the most suitable neighbourhood for the project's execution only started after the project had already been approved. AFC is a global network of the World Health Organization which Amsterdam Municipality has joined. Together with the Dutch public health service *GGD*, the council initiated a search for a suitable pilot area. The research group in question, which initially focused on a project on collaboration between formal and informal care providers, saw an opportunity to receive additional financing by establishing a link between its original fieldlab project and AFC. Perhaps as a result of these top-down preliminaries, no elderly individuals, care givers or care institutions were initially consulted. The neighbourhood was finally involved in the design and implementation phase. Several elderly individuals are even playing a special part as they are being trained as co-researchers and as such are interviewing their elderly fellow residents with regard to their wishes and needs in the neighbourhood.³¹ The local agenda of the neighbourhood, where the pilot is taking place, lists 'aging' as a current issue.³² In other words, in this fieldlab an urban project (AFC), with assistance from a fieldlab related research group, locates a suitable study area in urban district Amsterdam East. A win-win situation for the Amsterdam Municipality, district Amsterdam East, and the research group in question. But what about the elderly residents? Would an earlier involvement of this local party have contributed to another or even better outcome?

The project *Climate resilient Neighbourhood* originated in the research group 'Water

³⁰ 110 Dagen Plan Fieldlab Oost 2014; Majoor, Stan (2016). 'Inleiding' in: Werken in een gebied: gewoon doen in Amsterdam. Amsterdam Municipality: Project Management Bureau

³¹ Veldboer, Lex. (2016), Hoe ouderenvriendelijk vinden ouderen hun buurt? Research proposal Age Friendly City, Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences

³² Amsterdam Municipality (2016). Gebiedsplan Indische Buurt 2016. Consulted at <https://www.amsterdam.nl/bestuur-organisatie/volg-beleid/gebiedsgericht/gebiedsplannen-2016/gebiedsplannen-oost/gebiedsplan/>

in and around the city'. At first, this was a low-priority theme within the local administration.³³ However, the involved professor realized the urgency and complexity of the issue as early as 2014. During a fieldlab meeting he linked the research group to the theme and, later, to the structural maintenance trajectory in this neighbourhood. In this case, the 'question' arose out of what the research group together with the urban district's administrators could offer, in the form of a collaboration at the neighbourhood level and a joint learning process focussing on excessive water and heat stress.

The district Amsterdam East, the Space & Sustainability sector of the Municipality of Amsterdam, the local Water Institute, housing associations and neighbourhood organizations became interested. Once again, the role of local residents became important mainly in the project's design and implementation phases. In this case, an AUAS research group went looking for support among urban stakeholders in East to be able to start working with this theme. It also approached co-financers who might be willing to invest in experiments aimed at exploring new approaches to urban water management. In order to link potential project-specific co-financers to a fieldlab the study's added value needs to be clear from the start. Also, the project should transcend its local character and local needs. In order to justify the investment, yields in neighbourhood X should lend themselves to being transplanted to neighbourhood Y. The co-financers were necessary to make this fieldlab project possible. This gave them an important role in defining the issues and method.

A question-oriented strategy with the neighbourhood as a requesting party in the preparatory stage of a fieldlab project turns out to be a complicated task. Actors involved in the fieldlab, and in particular the research groups, function both as demanding and as a supplying party. As such they fulfil a pivotal role in the project's first phase. The city council and the co-financers have an important stake as well.

4 Looking for balance

The examples described above show that it was not evident from the start whose question was the focus of the fieldlab. Identifying purely bottom-up (resident) issues from the start was difficult. There are at least four reasons for this. First, Fieldlab East's familiarity with local networks and neighbourhoods was initially too limited to be able to arrive at a carefully considered selection of issues. The fieldlab did, however, at a later point reach back to a few earlier identified local issues by means

³³ Amsterdam Municipality (2016). *Gebiedsplan Watergraafsmeer 2016*. Consulted at <https://www.amsterdam.nl/bestuur-organisatie/volg-beleid/gebiedsgericht/gebiedsplannen-2016/gebiedsplannen-oost/gebiedsplan-2016/>

of neighbourhood agendas. Second, residents seldom speak with one voice. Therefore, they can never be addressed as one single stakeholder. Third, the neighbourhood is obviously not the only requesting party. Also, the district council has its own questions and needs to which it seeks answers and solutions through the fieldlab. Likewise, AUAS research groups are looking for areas or cases which they can use to apply and evaluate new methods and new procedures. Finally, co-financing – a necessary condition for starting a fieldlab project – is often decisive in the selection of the area. In the case of Fieldlab East, question-oriented strategies therefore equal multi-stakeholder strategies, in which the question ‘whose issues will be addressed first?’ determines the ultimate outcome. Equally crucial is the decision as to which stakeholders will be admitted to the interactive fieldlab trajectory and when, and how much manoeuvring room they will receive.

In the case of Fieldlab East, it became apparent that the involved professors and area-based public professionals had a significant role in the selection of the research topics and study area. The residents, as ‘bottom up’ stakeholders, only played a minor part in deciding the themes. They were more prominently present in the design and implementation phases. A bottom up strategy in the first phase demanded apparently more attention and local knowledge of the neighbourhood. For now, the field lab team accepted this procedure; the justification of a question-oriented strategy lies after all not (solely) in providing what residents as end users want, but (also) in helping to solve a particular metropolitan problem. This requires a co-creation process with all relevant parties.

In a fieldlab, the objective is to strike an acceptable balance for all requesting parties in order to create a structural interaction between them which all can accept. If this can be accomplished, a fieldlab as a community of practice is able to draw upon local knowledge, to empower residents, to make a neighbourhood resilient and to offer professionals a robust network in which they can make a difference. One more step, and a ‘co-city’ emerges, characterized by co-creative administrative structures in which multiple parties share a sense of collective ownership and take responsibility for an area, a task, a common.³⁴

In order to avoid semantic tricks and false expectations, a fieldlab team should make clear from the beginning whose question is considered and in which phase. The two examples from Amsterdam East show that the research group are the most present and dominant partner in the start-up phase of a fieldlab. In an effort to improve the question-oriented approach with a prominent role for the ‘locals’ from the start, I will conclude by offering a suggestion to make this possible in the context of the AUAS

³⁴ Ibidem

fieldlabs. Instead of substantial financial investments by AUAS, the municipality and co-financers from the moment a research plan is approved, a professor interested in doing research in the context of a fieldlab could apply for 'seed money'. For a period of six to twelve months, researchers and students visit a neighbourhood to explore a number of local, 'bottom up' issues that have links with the research group, and build a network. Following this preliminary study, the research group, on behalf of the neighbourhood, and the urban district file a plan in which the three parties argue why they require funding to carry out a one or two-year follow-up study of the issue. During this stage, the fieldlab team and research group search for co-financers and convince them that they have a relevant and widely supported case on their hands which will benefit from more research and experimentation. In this way the question-oriented method can become truly bottom-up.